

Exponential Feature Extraction and Learning for Pixel-Wise Hyperspectral Image Compression

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Abstract

Hyperspectral images are captured over a wide range of the electromagnetic spectrum providing detailed information about the Earth's surface. Hyperspectral imaging is widely used in agriculture, astronomy, molecular biology, physics, etc. Due to the very large size of information that the remotely-sensed hyperspectral data cube contains, transmission is a challenge. Various hyperspectral image compression techniques have been proposed in the last decades. We propose a new lossy compression technique that is based on the Fast Fourier Transform, negative exponential feature extraction, and machine learning. For the Pavia University data set, we obtained a compression rate of approximately 11, while preserving an important amount of the information in the original scene. Furthermore, we visualized the decompressed data starting from only two retained parameters and we evaluated the results by employing various metrics.

1 Introduction

Imaging spectroscopy, which is also referred to as hyperspectral imaging, focuses on acquiring spectra over a wide range of the electromagnetic spectrum, in every point of a particular scene or object [1]. Remote sensing hyperspectral imaging uses sensors located on aircraft or satellites at various altitudes from Earth's surface. This process involves measuring, analyzing, and interpreting the acquired data [2]. The concept was introduced by Goetz et al. (1985) [3]. Hyperspectral imaging is widely used in agriculture, astronomy, molecular biology, physics, etc., as hyperspectral images (HSIs) provide detailed spectral information about the reflected electromagnetic radiation. However, HSIs are large in size, thus, various approaches have been proposed to compress HSIs for more efficient data transfer and storage while preserving essential information.

HSI compression techniques can be based on transforms, prediction, learning, vector quantization, etc [4]. With lossless compression techniques, a maximum compression rate of 3 can be achieved, which may be insufficient in many applications [5]. One of the approaches is based on utilizing principal component analysis (PCA) in JPEG2000 for spectral decorrelation and dimensionality reduction. Rate-distortion performance and information preservation capabilities are assessed and compared to the standard JPEG2000 wavelet-based approach. Results indicate that the PCA-based coder outperforms the wavelet-based one, with the best performance achieved when fewer principal components are retained. A linear model to estimate the optimal number of principal components for dimensionality reduction is also suggested [6]. A lossless compression technique which combines adaptive classified arithmetic coding in the wavelet domain with an adaptive spectral band reordering algorithm was proposed in [7]. By dividing residual images post-wavelet transform into distinct classes and applying adaptive arithmetic coding to each class, the algorithm saves significant coding bits. The adaptive reordering algorithm effectively utilizes spectral correlation by identifying an optimal reference band for each band. A more detailed review of the HSI compression techniques can be found in [4].

Our approach for compression is based on the following two hypotheses: (i) a negative exponential function can approximate good enough the Fourier spectrum of a pixel hyperspectral reflectance curve; and (ii) a Neural Network (NN) is capable of learning the correspondence between the negative exponential function and the real spectral reflectance curve. Here the negative exponential function can be used to represent the essential information while discarding the rest, leading to a significant reduction in data volume. The second hypothesis builds on recent advances in machine learning, which have shown that NN is capable of learning complex patterns and relationships in data. In our case, the NN can learn to identify the relationship between the negative exponential function and the spectral reflectance curve, thus enabling effective compression of hyperspectral images. The methodology is described in Section 2 while experimental results are described in Section 3. Finally, conclusions are provided in Section 4.

2 Methodology

The proposed approach has the following steps: we apply the Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) to the pixel hyperspectral reflectance $R(\lambda)$; we consider only half the values of the FFT spectrum due to the symmetry; we fit the negative exponential curve of the form $f(x) = a \cdot e^{-bx}$ to the FFT amplitude and obtain the two parameters (a, b) [8]; afterward, we store a and b parameters as compressed pixel data. In preparation for the decompression

step, we feed the NN with the same extracted negative exponential function and we train the NN to learn the correspondence between the extracted exponential features and the original pixel hyperspectral signature. Before feeding the data to the NN, we eliminate the second half of the vector values which are close to zero. Figure 1 illustrates the proposed compression-decompression process.

Figure 1: The block diagram of the proposed pixel-wise compression-decompression approach.

For the learning stage, we designed a classical NN with three layers (input, hidden, and output), which will be used as well in the decompression stage to predict the real pixel spectral reflectance curve (see Figure 2). Specifically, we employed a backpropagation algorithm with Adam optimizer and ReLU activation function for the neurons in the hidden layer. The number of neurons on the input, hidden and output layers depends on the number of bands in the hyperspectral image, as well as the proposed approach. As an example, for the case of Pavia University HSI, which has 103 spectral bands, the number of input neurons is 25 since they have been reduced after the FFT to 51 bands, due to FFT’s symmetry, and further on to only 25 bands by elimination of the very small values (the second half of the vector). The output layer consists of 103 neurons as the number of spectral bands in the original Pavia University HSI and the hidden layer size is defined by the average number of neurons on the input and the output layers. In Figure 3 we illustrate the feature extraction process for a pixel spectral reflectance curve.

For experiments, we chose Pavia University HSI, for which the spectral cube has the dimensions of $610 \times 340 \times 103$. Moreover, we used Python and Tensorflow libraries for implementing the NN while the rest of the steps were implemented in MATLAB. We used approximately 20% of the pixel spectral values of the considered HSI for training the NN. After the compression and learning step, the original image was reconstructed using the previously-

Figure 2: Architecture of the NN.

extracted exponential features (namely a and b parameters) and the output of the NN which predicted, for each pixel, the initial spectral reflectance curve.

3 Experimental Results

In Figure 4 (a) we show the gray-scale version of the original Pavia University image and in (b) and (c) we show the $\log(a)$ and b pseudo-images, which show that the Pavia University scene can be described by the extracted negative exponential features. The (a, b) feature pseudo-images are clearly correlated to the gray-scale image. In Table 1 we show the Pearson correlation coefficient (PCC) between the a, b features and various spectral bands of the original HSI, confirming the previous purely-visual observation. One may note that the $\log(a)$ pseudo-image exhibits a correlation larger than 0.7 with all the bands, while the b pseudo-image approx. 0.6.

Table 1: PCC between selected bands from the HSI and $\log(a)$, b matrices.

Band	b_3	b_5	b_{21}	b_{25}	b_{50}	b_{60}
$\log(a)$	0.7	0.72	0.73	0.72	0.78	0.77
b	-0.58	-0.59	-0.58	-0.55	-0.59	-0.59

In order to validate the proposed approach, we measured the similarity between the original HSI and the reconstructed one. More specifically, we measured the spectral similarity of each pixel by using the Spectral Angle Mapper (SAM) proposed in [9]. As it is shown in Figure 5, the histogram of the SAM values has a negative exponential shape, with an average of 0.0817 and the majority (approx. 93%) of the values concentrated in the interval $[0 - 0.2]$ and the maximum value of 1.2. We can conclude that the

(a)

(b)

Figure 3: A pixel spectral signature (a); and graph of the fitted exponential curve to the FFT (b).

Figure 4: Experimental results regarding the negative exponential feature extraction for the Pavia University data set.

extracted negative exponential features are good enough to approximate the FFT of pixel reflectance curves and the NN was capable of learning, with an acceptable error, the correspondence between the extracted features and the pixel spectral values.

In order to visualize the reconstructed image and to have a visual insight of the obtained experimental results, we chose to represent the color RGB composites of the original and reconstructed HSI using the band-selection approach for visualization (see Figure 6 (a) and (b), respectively). For visualization, the following three bands have been selected: 53, 21, 7 and mapped to the red, green, and blue channels, respectively. Then we linearized the RGB data cube for better visualization. One can note that the reconstructed image is very similar to the original one, but a lossy compression of the image is visible, mainly on the colors of the metal roofs. In order to objectively measure the similarity of the two colors RGB images, original and reconstructed, we used three metrics to evaluate the experimental results: Mean Absolute Error (MAE) [10], ΔE color difference [11] and Structural Similarity Index Measure (SSIM) [12]. For the Pavia University image, for the three evaluation metrics we obtained the following results: MAE= 3.71, $\Delta E = 4.2$, and SSIM= 0.97, which show that the similarity of the two images is very high. In addition, in Figure 6 (c) we depict the pseudo-image of ΔE color differences between the original and reconstructed Pavia University RGB color images. For the majority of pixels the $\Delta E < 20$ and for 30% of the pixels the $\Delta E < 3$, which is the threshold for

Figure 5: Histogram of the SAM values.

the just-noticeable difference.

We evaluated the performance of the proposed pixel-wise compression-decompression mechanism in terms of the data compression rate. The 2D matrices of a and b extracted features have a total size of 3.01 MB (stored as a MATLAB file), while the original Pavia University HSI has 33.1 MB (.mat). Thus, the achieved compression ratio is 10.9967. In Figure 7 we show a pixel spectral signature of the original Pavia University HSI and the reconstructed version, as a middle-case example (more pixels spectral signatures follow more closely the original ones, while for some others may vary significantly).

Figure 6: Experimental results for the band-selection color composite of Pavia University data set.

Figure 7: Original pixel spectral signature and the reconstructed.

4 Conclusions

We proposed a lossy compression-decompression technique based on FFT, negative exponential feature extraction and machine learning. We used Pavia University hyperspectral data cube that has a 33.1 MB size, while the compressed size is 3.01 MB, the achieved compression rate being 10.9967. The extracted and then learnt exponential features contain the essential information of the original HSI, as indicated by the visualization as grayscale images and the computed correlation coefficient. Moreover, the band-selection color composite of the scene after the decompression exhibits very good similarity to the original. However, losses in the color information are visible and they can be observed mainly on the cyan roofs. Further, we used Spectral Angle Mapper for validating the spectral similarity between the original and reconstructed HSI. Mean Absolute Error, color difference, and Structural Similarity Index Measure were used to evaluate RGB images of original and reconstructed HSI. We can conclude that the experimental results prove the two working hypotheses.

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References

- [1] M. J. Khan, H. S. Khan, A. Yousaf, K. Khurshid, and A. Abbas, “Modern trends in hyperspectral image analysis: A review,” *IEEE Access*, vol. 6, 2018.
- [2] “Recent advances in techniques for hyperspectral image processing,” *Remote Sensing of Environment*, vol. 113, pp. S110–S122, 2009. Imaging Spectroscopy Special Issue.
- [3] A. F. H. Goetz, G. Vane, J. E. Solomon, and B. N. Rock, “Imaging spectrometry for earth remote sensing,” *Science*, vol. 228, no. 4704, pp. 1147–1153, 1985.
- [4] Y. Dua, V. Kumar, and R. S. Singh, “Comprehensive review of hyperspectral image compression algorithms,” *Optical Engineering*, vol. 59, 2020.
- [5] J. Serra-Sagristà and F. Aulí-Llinàs in *Computational Intelligence for Remote Sensing*, pp. 27–61, Springer-Verlag, 2008.
- [6] Q. Du and J. E. Fowler, “Hyperspectral image compression using jpeg2000 and principal component analysis,” *IEEE Geoscience and Remote Sensing Letters*, vol. 4, no. 2, pp. 201–205, 2007.
- [7] J. Zhang and G. Liu, “A novel lossless compression for hyperspectral images by adaptive classified arithmetic coding in wavelet domain,” in *2006 International Conference on Image Processing*, pp. 2269–2272, 2006.
- [8] J. Schlesinger, “Fit to experimental data with exponential functions using the fast fourier transform,” *Nuclear Instruments and Methods*, vol. 106, 1973.

- [9] F. van der Meer, “The effectiveness of spectral similarity measures for the analysis of hyperspectral imagery,” *International Journal of Applied Earth Observation and Geoinformation*, vol. 8, 2006.
- [10] Y. Hashidume and Y. Morikawa, “Lossless image coding based on minimum mean absolute error predictors,” *Proceedings of the SICE Annual Conference*, pp. 2832–2836, 2007.
- [11] S. P. Farnand, “Using ΔE metrics for measuring color difference in hard copy pictorial images,” in *Color Imaging VIII: Processing, Hardcopy, and Applications*, vol. 5008, pp. 109 – 118, International Society for Optics and Photonics, SPIE, 2003.
- [12] Z. Wang, A. Bovik, H. R. Sheikh, and E. P. Simoncelli, “Image quality assessment: from error visibility to structural similarity,” *IEEE Transactions on Image Processing*, vol. 13, pp. 600–612, 2004.